

BRIEFING

youth
SKILLS

Dear teacher, educator, researcher or other stakeholder,

The ySKILLS research team is excited to introduce you to this valuable resource designed to engage children and adolescents in learning about digital skills of young people. This collection of materials and activities is the result of extensive research within the ySKILLS project. More details on the project can be found on the website: www.yskills.eu.

This briefing document aims to provide you with information on the content and practical aspects of this toolkit.

WHAT?

The child-friendly summary, presented in the form of a PowerPoint presentation, summarizes the main ySKILLS research results from 2022 in a way that is accessible and understandable for children and adolescents **between 12 and 17 years old**.

As teacher, educator, researcher or other stakeholder, your role is to act as intermediary, helping young people navigate through the content and facilitating meaningful group discussions.

The toolkit is divided into **five modules**, each addressing different aspects of digital skills. These modules include:

1. What are digital skills?
2. What do we know from research about digital skills?
3. How do we measure digital skills?
4. Survey results on digital skills among young people in Europe
5. How to improve your digital skills?

The duration of the entire toolkit (the five modules) is approximately **one class session** (+/- 40 minutes). We also offer you the flexibility to focus on only a few modules, or to use the extra slides for a follow-up session.

Additionally, for some activities the toolkit offers **multiple layers of difficulty levels**, allowing you to adapt the content to meet the diverse needs of young people.

SESSION OBJECTIVES

1. Young people understand what digital skills are, why they matter, and how they can be measured.
2. Young people reflect on their own digital skills and make sense of the key ySKILLS findings (e.g., they give it meaning, enrich the insights with their own lived experience, they compare their own digital skills to those of other young people in Europe).
3. Young people learn about the link between digital skills and online risks.
4. Young people learn how they can improve their own digital skills.

SESSION MATERIALS

- This briefing document, digitally or printed.
- PowerPoint presentation, including speaker notes.
- Projector or large screen.
- *Optional: online poll tool for the self-assessment and/or quiz*
- *Optional: internet access and digital devices such as smartphone or laptop for young people to use the online poll tool.*
- *Optional: papers and coloured pens for the optional activity on course design.*

PREPARATION

- Read this briefing document. If necessary, print the overview of the session structure.
- Get familiar with the PowerPoint. Make sure that you feel confident with the content and the activities of all slides. The slides contain speaker notes to explain what the slide is about, to help you contextualise the information presented in the slides and to give inspiration for discussion questions.
- Decide which difficulty level you will adopt and hide the alternative slide(s).
- Decide whether you will show the optional follow-up activities. If necessary, hide the optional slides.
- *Optional: create an online poll with the self-assessment and quiz questions.*

SESSION STRUCTURE

CONTENT	SLIDE	NOTES
INTRODUCTION	1-2	Introducing the session, plus self-assessment activity to reflect on young people's digital skills level. You can optionally use an online polling tool for this activity.
MODULE 1: What are digital skills?	3-8	Overview of four types of digital skills and examples.
MODULE 2: What do we know from research about digital skills?	9-18	Exploring research on digital skills of young people via a quiz. There are two options: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• An easier set with one statement each: true or false? (Slide 11-16)• A more challenging slide that combines multiple statements: "Which one is false?" (Slide 17 and 18 - you might consider combining this slide with the statement on gender (slide 16), so that you have two slides on this topic)
MODULE 3: How do we measure digital skills?	19-22	Introducing an instrument to measure young people's digital skills, including an action question. There are two alternatives for this practical task: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Easy version (Slide 21), and/or• More challenging version + smartphone/laptop required (Slide 22) You can optionally use an online polling tool for this activity.
MODULE 4: Survey results on digital skills among young people in Europe	23-27	Exploring findings from the ySKILLS survey on digital skills of young people in Europe. Young people can guess the numbers and results, and reflect on their own situation. Via a quote, young people discuss the use of digital technologies and mental health.
MODULE 5: How to improve your digital skills?	28-31	Exploring four ways to improve digital skills of young people. Optional activities for an extra session: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Design your ideal course on digital skills at school (Slide 29).• Share the results with the world: youth participation (Slide 31). This activity can strengthen young people's understandings of digital citizenship and participation in and engagement with science. Please allow at least 10-15 minutes for this activity.
CLOSING	32-33	Gathering feedback and sharing of ySKILLS channels.

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